

WITH CHARGE MELTING METHODS AND LOW METAL CONTENT IN THE FURNACE EFFECT OF ELECTRODES

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Abstract: Here a new direct current electric arc furnace is designed and constructed. a study on the experimental investigation of high-titanium slag smelting with emphasis issues of incomplete separation of metal and slag, as well as poor insulation effect. Mechanic components (crucible, electrode, furnace lining, etc.) are designed and engineered and embedded a crucible design was adopted to promote metal-slag separation. Lining and bottom thickness was determined computationally using the furnace heat balance equations, which improved thermal insulation. appropriate software has been developed to monitor electrical parameters. A series of tests were conducted to determine the optimum for evaluating the performance of the furnace addition of coke under conditions of constant temperature (1600-1650 °C) and melting time (80-90 min). The The results showed that 5% coke was the highest for metallized pellets containing 12 kg of titanium. Effective for enriching TiO₂ high titanium alloy, TiO₂ content reaches 90%. In addition, it met the design requirements in terms of thickness and made the process easier several processes for the separation of metal-slugs that show satisfactory performance during experiments have been cited.

Keywords: Electric stove, high titanium alloys, mechanical design, software development, metal melting furnaces.

Introduction

The article is devoted to numerical simulation of electromagnetic processes in new metallurgy oven. Compared to other well-known methods of iron and steel production, this the furnace is more efficient and environmentally friendly. Numerical simulation is widely used A lot of thermal energy is used to simulate the processes that occur in metallurgy, in particular, steel melting furnaces. Conducting experiments in metallurgy is expensive and extremely complicated. The simplest and the most effective way to evaluate processes in furnaces is the numerical simulation method. Numeric string simulation and analysis of results

allows optimization and organization of steel production operations ovens. Steel casting furnaces need constant modernization and quality improvement in the process of melting the metal, the quantity of the produced product decreases. cost reduction and improvement operating conditions have been examined in several experimental studies. In the context of high and unstable prices of scrap metal and cast iron used in steel production it becomes relevant to use not only ore materials, but also metallized raw materials obtained from it industrial waste can be achieved as a partial replacement of traditional types of charge. Man-made waste that was previously collected and recycled at metallurgical enterprises development of new energy-saving and environmentally friendly technologies for their processing according to Laboratory studies on the treatment of iron-containing waste in an electric furnace was carried out in two stages: the first stage of solid-phase initial recovery, waste a furnace chamber with a reservoir for waste gases that simultaneously heats the charge and secondly, the liquid phase stage in the furnace bath for the production of cast iron. Titanium dioxide is an important inorganic chemical material that is widely used coating, papermaking, rubber, chemical fiber and other industries. It is widely used in industry, agriculture and production. Because it contains less titanium titanium resources cannot be used directly to produce the main titanium ore the method of melting titanium dioxide and titanium slag should be used to meet the needs. Usually, it is used to heat and melt ilmenite, so it is enriched with high content. TiO_2 is obtained after separation of TiO_2 and iron in ilmenite. It is a raw material we can see the separation process of ilmenite and carbon according to the following chemical reaction.

Methods and processes of the first numerical simulation

According to the technological scheme of the process shown in Picture. 1, metal production includes the following operations:

- * continuous loading of premixed components of the charge into the furnace shaft, in which counterflow conditions with the initial solid phase of the process hot exhaust gases decline occurs;
- * melting of charged materials and contraction of the liquid phase metal due to the released Joule heat slag bath during the passage of electric current between the lower electrodes, as well as inside the process of oxidation of charged carbon and metal bath with gaseous oxygen;
- * periodic production of metal solutions - reducing the amount of liquid metal and alloy through special tap holes

Picture 1. Technological scheme of metallurgy furnace and process status are given.

In addition, the complex environment inside the furnace with increased melting times accelerates the erosion (carbon consumption) of the inner wall of the crucible; however, often replacement of the crucible, due to these factors, leads to high maintenance costs. That is why, in our case, a small moving crucible is placed in a large crucible for melting. After melting, the product solidified and the crucible was removed and dissected to obtain the product. This the process effectively prevents mixing of slag and liquid metal during dumping process and thus crucible degradation, thereby reducing high maintenance costs. The energy transformation of an experimental metal melting furnace is non-linear and multi-stage process; however, according to the law of equilibrium, the energy input of the electrode must be equal to the energy produced for the whole unit and for each of its zones, as shown in Picture 2. In the figure, the arrow shows the direction of energy transfer.

Picture 2. Schematic diagram showing heat transfer inside a metal melting furnace.

Conclusions

Liquid-phase carbon-thermal melting-reduction process in a double-bottom electric furnace electrodes were designed and tested under laboratory conditions. The process is not important for selection materials containing charged iron. It can be scale, dust and mud from the furnace steel production. The use of lower electrodes can significantly reduce or increase equipment investment costs energy efficiency and environmental safety of the process are ensured.

1. The mechanical structure is developed, which includes the power supply mode, electrode and electrode holder, electric circuit, crucible and reaction chamber structure. The buried design of the crucible was used to separate the metal and slag is used in processes. In addition, surface finish and bottom thickness were determined the use of heat balance equations is envisaged.

2. Factors of metal melting efficiency were analyzed. Voltage, current, melt Experimental electrode time and temperature data collected by Electric Metal melting Furnaces and a system for monitoring their electrical parameters was developed.

3. Optimum weight percentage in metal melting furnace performance evaluation test reduction processes were investigated. The results show that for separation of 12 kg temperature (1600-1650 °C) and metallized granules containing titanium during melting time (80-90 min) was constant, coke with 5% coke by total weight was the most effective conditions for alleviating the enrichment effect of TiO₂ in high-titanium alloys are presented; therefore, the amount of TiO₂ in the alloy reached 90%. It indicates that it is offered meets the design requirements of the thickness and achieves a good result facilitated several complex processes in metal-slag separation processes. O'telbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, gave several examples of the processes of their application in mining and presented to international journals the methods of automation of mining technologies through microprocessors and the technologies in mining at the same time. proved with several examples that it can be used in several technological processes. The use of modern technologies plays an important role in the development economy of the mine. It is necessary to pay attention to the parameters of technologies when automating processes in mining enterprises. Do not set the load beyond the limits of the technology, only then the technology

will work for a long time without problems. In this article, I will inform you that if we install a microprocessor (automatic mode memory) in the technology in the mining enterprises, we will prevent the overloading of the technology. This ensures the operation of the enterprise and the safety of workers. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, has articles on metallurgical processes, components of metals, and metal enrichment processes. Much research has been done on the metallurgical industry. A number of information on processes in metallurgical deposits, extraction of metals, corrosion of metals and extraction of metals by flotation methods are presented

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